

ONLINE DATA AND THEIR SECURITY SUPPORT

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Annotation: this article is written about the protection of information and information on the internet from various cyber attacks and its security.

Keywords: cyber, security, electron government, information :

Today, along with the expansion of relations in the field of informatization in our society, new social relations aimed at preventing offensive offenses in this area in our country have become one of the pressing issues of ensuring information security. State institution of the Center for information security under the Ministry of development of information technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures for the further development of the National Information and communication system of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2013 119 - It was organized in accordance with the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 16, 2013 No. 250 on measures to organize the activities of the Center for the development of the electronic government system and the Center for information security under the state committee for communication informatization and telecommunication technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Information Security Center is the only state institution in Uzbekistan for technical and consultative assistance in ensuring information security in the collection and analysis of information on computer phenomena. Sources may be accidental and intended to prevent application failures in the supply failure of technical means failure of qualifications or user errors are considered random surpluses. The appointment is carried out in order to damage the information reserves. They are active and inactive. Inactive threats include aspirations for unauthorized use of information reserves without affecting their functions. Active threats aimed at disrupting the functioning of the system's substances by influencing the information reserves on technical and software tools are the easiest way to eliminate this risk in advance and apply precautions against it. From this point of view, both in terms of ensuring information security and in relation to the industry, the identification of sources of patency order and numerous coding of protective measures are among the primary tasks. Sources of threat to information security are divided into internal and external sources. Experts admit that the actual

problem of information security was caused mainly by external sources, since today information is mentioned as the main means of the struggle for ownership of the modern world. In such a situation, Information Technology and information management are literally benefits from the use of this advantage in themselves by highly developed countries in the way of influencing social consciousness. The emergence of the information space has led to the emergence of parties who want not only to take place, but also to control and control the processes taking place in it. The tool for the struggle of orders is also an information weapon, which analysts call tools that mentally affect people and allow control over them computer viruses logical bomb in telecommunication networks, referring to such costs as falsification of information in the management of devices suppressing information exchange in the state and military spheres. The main means of influence of threats to information security are one-time Organization shares long-term propaganda companies ideological style cultural expansion information blockade natural mental information impact tools. Mental infarmactional media and global influence are carried out through the means of discrimination, and instilling distrust in the internal policy of the state stabilization of the internal social political situation in the eyes of the opposition mood among the population even the incitement of people to rebellion can have natural negative consequences. It is impossible to completely limit or control the means of mental informational influence on the globalized information field democratic governance the diversity of opinions does not allow this. In fact, every information that is being distributed must be checked over and over again. But reality does not allow this mirage to be realized. Hence the proverb that sought other solutions to the problem.

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